

**DESCRIPTION OF THE BLOOD AND CIRCULATORY SYSTEM OF WOMEN OF
REPRODUCTIVE AGE RESIDING IN DIFFERENT REGIONS OF THE REPUBLIC
OF KARACALPAKISTAN**

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***Аннотация:** В данной статье описаны изменения и проблемы состава крови женщин, проживающих в Республике Каракалпакстан, вследствие факторов окружающей среды, влияющих на их репродуктивное здоровье.*

***Ключевые слова:** Репродуктивная функция, здоровье женщины, кровь, лейкоциты, тромбоциты, эритроциты, реформа, материнство и детство, медицинская помощь, окружающая среда.*

***Abstract:** This article describes the changes and problems in the blood composition of women living in the Republic of Karakalpakstan due to environmental factors affecting their reproductive health.*

***Keywords:** reproductive, women's health, blood, leukocytes, platelets, erythrocytes, reform, motherhood and childhood, medical care, environment.*

In the human body, blood and lymph are the inner world. Blood is a weakly alkaline liquid with a specific gravity of 1.054-1.066. There is a total of 5 liters of blood in the human body and it makes up 7-8% of the body weight.

Also, blood performs several important vital functions:

A) the blood distributes nutrients absorbed from the intestines throughout the canal. Because the blood plasma is in the tissue and intercellular space, all the nutrients can quickly enter the cells. Later, these nutrients are broken down inside the cells and used for the needs of the body;

B) blood delivers oxygen to all tissues and carries carbon dioxide produced there to the lungs. The blood passing through the pulmonary capillaries is saturated with oxygen there and adds carbon dioxide to the air coming out of the lungs;

C) blood is the main defender of the body, it destroys and neutralizes various foreign and toxic substances. Various foreign microorganisms entering the body from outside are neutralized by white blood cells - leukocytes;

D) blood keeps the body temperature at the same level. It flows to all peripheral organs and brings heat along with it. Because the blood moves intensively through the skin, excess temperature is transferred to the environment and the body is protected from overheating [1].

Due to the constant movement of the blood, the body is cleaned of unnecessary residual substances formed as a result of metabolism, that is, they flow with the blood to the kidneys and skin and are excreted from there.

For every organism to live a normal life, it needs constant blood circulation. Continuous blood movement in blood vessels occurs due to the activity of special azo-heart, artery blood vessels, and transverse fiber muscles. The body has a special system that manages blood circulation to supply all organs and systems with blood in various situations. Due to the work of this system, the demand for oxygen and nutrients of all tissues and cells is met under different conditions.

Based on the above information, blood is an important part of the human body. It performs many functions. Violation of the composition of blood directly prevents it from fully fulfilling its function in the body. As a result, various pathologies appear and develop in the body. Today, a significant part of the population living in the Republic of Karakalpakstan, which is considered one of the ecologically problematic regions of Uzbekistan, suffers from various pathologies related to blood. In particular, in March-April of this year, the results of blood analysis of women of reproductive age living in the Amudarya and Karauzyak districts of the Republic and the city of Nukus were studied. According to the results of the analysis, 10 out of 41 women living in the Amudarya region had hemoglobin, 21 erythrocytes, 22 thrombocytes, 28 leukocyte types eosinophils, and 37 monocytes were found to be below the specified norm. Among 22 women of reproductive age living in the Karauzyak district, 22 have hemoglobin, 22 erythrocytes, 22 thrombocytes, and 1 leukocyte type has a lower-than-normal level of monocytes. Also, according to the results of blood analysis of 37 women of this age living in Nukus, 20 of them had hemoglobin, 10 erythrocytes, 15 platelets, and 18 leukocytes.

In general, if we talk about the extent to which the lack or excess of these units in the blood affects human health and what causes their increase or decrease, it is appropriate to talk about hemoglobin (HB) first of all. Hemoglobin is a protein containing an iron atom that can bind and transport oxygen. Hemoglobin is found in red blood cells (erythrocytes). Hemoglobin is measured in grams per liter (g/l). Determination of the amount of hemoglobin is very important because its decrease leads to a lack of oxygen to the tissues and organs of the whole body [2,434].

Causes of low hemoglobin (anemia):

- Anemia;
- Leukemia;
- Congenital blood diseases (sickle cell anemia, thalassemia);
- Lack of iron;
- Lack of vitamins;
- Blood loss.

Factors that increase hemoglobin:

- Dehydration (depletion of fluid in the body (thirst), excessive sweating, reduced kidney function, diabetes, diabetes insipidus, excessive vomiting or diarrhea, use of diuretics);
- Congenital heart and lung defects;
- Lung failure or heart failure;
- Kidney disease (renal artery stenosis, benign kidney tumors);
- Diseases of hematopoiesis (production of blood elements) (erythremia);

Erythrocytes are small red blood cells. These are the most abundant blood cells. Their main task is to transport oxygen and deliver it to organs and tissues. Erythrocytes are in the form of concave discs on both sides. Erythrocytes contain a large amount of hemoglobin - a large part of the red disc is occupied by them.

Factors that reduce red blood cells:

A decrease in the number of red blood cells is called anemia. Many factors contribute to the development of this condition, and they are not always related to the blood production system.

- Mistakes in nutrition (food with low amounts of vitamins and proteins);
- Blood loss;
- Leukemia (white blood pathology);
- Hereditary enzymopathy (defects of enzymes involved in hematopoiesis);
- Hemolysis (death of blood cells due to exposure to toxic substances and autoimmune diseases);

Leukocytes are living cells of the body that circulate in the bloodstream. These cells control the immune system. When an infection, toxin, or other foreign substance injures the body, these cells fight the damaging factors and try to destroy them. Leukocytes are produced in red bone marrow and lymph nodes. Leukocytes are divided into several types: neutrophils, basophils, eosinophils, monocytes, and lymphocytes. Different types of leukocytes differ in appearance and function in the immune response.

Factors that increase white blood cells (leukocytes):

Physiological increase in the number of leukocytes

- After meals;
- After active physical activity;
- In the second half of pregnancy;
- After vaccination;
- During menstruation.

Against the background of the inflammatory reaction

- Purulent inflammatory processes (abscess, phlegmon, bronchitis, sinusitis, sinusitis, appendicitis, etc.);

- Burns and injuries that damage soft tissues;
- After the operation;
- During exacerbation of rheumatism;
- In oncological processes;
- In leukemia pathology;

Factors of a decrease in the number of leukocytes:

- Viral and infectious diseases (infectious diseases, typhoid, viral hepatitis C, sepsis, measles, malaria, rubella, SARS, AIDS);
- Rheumatic diseases (rheumatic arthritis);
- Some types of leukemia;
- Hypovitaminosis;
- Radiation sickness;

The leukocyte formula is the percentage ratio of the number of different leukocytes in the blood to the total amount of leukocytes. In infectious, blood diseases, and oncological processes, the ratio of different types of leukocytes changes. Due to these laboratory indicators, the doctor can determine the causes of health problems [3., 435].

Eosinophils are a type of leukocytes involved in cleaning toxic substances, and parasites, participating in the fight against cancer cells. This type of leukocyte is directly involved in the formation of humoral immunity (antibody-related immunity).

Causes of increased blood eosinophils:

- Allergy (bronchial asthma, food allergy, pollinosis, atopic dermatitis, allergic rhinitis, drug allergy);
- Parasitic diseases - intestinal parasites (lambiosis, ascariasis, enterobiosis, opisthorchosis, echinococcosis);
- Infectious pathologies (tuberculosis, mononucleosis, venous diseases);

- Cancerous tumors;
- Diseases of the hematopoietic system (leukemia, lymphoma, lymphogranulomatosis);
- Rheumatic diseases (rheumatoid arthritis).

Factors that decrease eosinophils in the blood:

- Heavy metal poisoning;
- Purulent processes, sepsis;
- The beginning of the inflammatory process [4., 49].

Monocytes are the largest immune cells in the body. These white blood cells recognize foreign substances and teach other leukocytes to recognize them. They can move from the blood to the tissues of the body. Outside the bloodstream, monocytes change their appearance and become macrophages. Macrophages gather at the site of inflammation to participate in the cleaning of inflamed tissues from dead cells, leukocytes, and bacteria. Due to this work of macrophages, conditions are created for the recovery of damaged tissues.

Factors of monocyte proliferation (monocytosis):

- Infections caused by viruses, fungi (candidiasis), parasites and simple animals;
- Recovery period after the acute inflammatory process;
- Specific diseases: tuberculosis, malaria, brucellosis, sarcoidosis;
- Rheumatic diseases;
- Hematopoietic diseases: acute leukemia, myeloma, lymphogranulomatosis;
- Phosphorus, tetrachloroethane poisoning.

Factors that decrease monocytes (monocytopenia):

- Aplastic anemia;
- Hairy cell leukemia;
- Purulent wounds (abscesses, phlegmons, osteomyelitis);
- Childbirth process;
- After surgery;

- Taking steroid drugs (dexamethasone, prednisolone).

Platelets are small cells without a nucleus. The main function of this blood component is to directly participate in blood clotting. Thrombocytes contain most of the coagulation (clotting) factors and are injected into the blood at the right time (for example, when the vessel wall is damaged). Due to this feature, the damaged vessel becomes blocked by the thrombus forming a clot and the bleeding stops.

Reasons for a decrease in platelets in the blood:

(thrombocytopenia - less than 180×10^9 cells/l)

- Congenital blood diseases (hemophilia);
- Idiopathic autoimmune thrombocytopenic purpura;
- Systemic lupus erythematosus;
- Infection (viral and bacterial infections, malaria, toxoplasmosis);
- Aplastic anemia;
- Paroxysmal evening hemoglobinuria;
- Evans syndrome (autoimmune hemolytic anemia and thrombocytopenia);
- Blood transfusion;
- Premature birth in children;
- Heart failure;
- Thrombosis of renal veins;

In general, it can be concluded from the above considerations that the lack of certain blood cells in the blood of women of reproductive age living in the territory of Karakalpakstan, or, on the contrary, the excess of some of them, is caused by an environmental factor. Salt dust storms caused by the construction of the island in the territory of the republic, as well as atmospheric air pollution caused by industrial waste, are some of the leading factors in the occurrence of various pathological symptoms in the blood and circulatory system of the population.

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